

Supplementary tables: Table S1. Components of CR cell expansion media

Components	Concentration	Supplier	Catalogue number
DMEM/Ham's F-12	67%	Sigma	Cat#51651C
DMEM, high glucose	33%	Sigma	Cat#D5796
Fetal bovine serum	5% (v/v)	Interpath	Cat#SFBSF15
Penicillin-Streptomycin	0.2% (v/v)	Life Tech	Cat#15070-063
Hydrocortisone	400ng/ml	Sigma	Cat#H0888
Insulin	5µg/ml	Sigma	Cat#I0516
Cholera toxin	8.4ng/ml	Sigma	Cat#C8052
hEGF	10ng/ml	Bioscientific	Cat#236-EG-200
Adenine	23.9µg/ml	Sigma	Cat#A2786
Y-27632	10µM	Enzo life sciences	Cat#ALX-270-333-M025